

Protecting-Group-Free Mechanosynthesis of Amides from Hydroxycarboxylic Acids: Application to the Synthesis of Imatinib

Tatsiana Nikonovich,^a Tatsiana Jarg,^a Jevgenija Martõnova,^a Artjom Kudrjašov,^{a,b} Danylo Merzhyievskyi,^{a,c} Marina Kudrjašova,^a Fabrice Gallou,^d Riina Aav,^{a*} and Dzmitry Kananovich^{a*}

^a *Department of Chemistry and Biotechnology, Tallinn University of Technology, Akadeemia tee 15, 12618, Tallinn, Estonia*

^b *Tallinna Tõnismäe Reaalkool, Pärnu mnt 50, Tallinn, Estonia*

^c *Department of Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-containing Heterocyclic Bases, V. P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Academician Kukhar Str. 1, 02094 Kyiv, Ukraine*

^d *Novartis Pharma AG; Novartis Campus, 4056 Basel, Switzerland; orcid.org/0000-0001-8996-6079; e-mail: fabrice.gallou@novartis.com*

*Corresponding authors: Riina Aav, riina.aav@taltech.ee; Dzmitry Kananovich, dzmitry.kananovich@taltech.ee

Abstract: Mechanochemical methods for assembling carbon-nitrogen bonds play a central role in the ongoing green chemistry-driven renovation of organic synthesis, including the synthesis of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). However, chemoselective issues in these transformations, such as the tolerance of unmasked hydroxyl groups, have not been systematically explored. Screening of various amide coupling conditions revealed that 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) in combination with ethyl acetate as a liquid-assisted grinding (LAG) solvent was the most selective amide coupler, delivering 76–94% yields of the respective amide products from unprotected hydroxycarboxylic acids. Boc-protected tyrosine and serine with unmasked hydroxyl functionalities were successfully involved in peptide couplings. By incorporating green chemistry principles as a driver for innovation, the established protocol was applied to the synthesis of imatinib, an anticancer drug included in the World Health Organization’s List of Essential Medicines. The target API was synthesized with an overall yield of 86% and 99% HPLC purity through a two-step mechanochemical C–N bond assembling reaction sequence starting from 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid. A comparison of green chemistry metrics between the developed mechanochemical approach and similar solution-based approaches revealed reduced waste generation, enhanced eco-friendliness, and a superior safety profile for the proposed strategy. The safety improvement was primarily attributed to the elimination of toxic solvents and a genotoxic intermediate from the production chain.

Keywords: Mechanochemistry; Imatinib; Pharmaceuticals; Protecting-group-free synthesis; Amines; Amides.

Introduction

The modern pharmaceutical industry is increasingly focused on sustainable production processes and innovative technologies that minimize environmental impacts¹ and comply with green chemistry principles.² Mechanochemistry,³⁻⁶ an essentially solvent-free technique, has shown great potential as a powerful tool for advancing the sustainability goals in the synthesis of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs).⁷⁻¹¹ By eliminating solvents from the production chain, mechanochemistry can offer improved safety profiles and minimize the amount of generated waste,¹² as solvents can account for up to 90% of the total mass consumed and are major contributors to the overall toxicity profile in a typical industrial process.¹³

Nitrogen-containing functional groups predominate in bioactive molecules¹⁴ and carbon-nitrogen (C–N) bond-forming reactions are widely used in the synthesis of APIs. For instance, nitrogen atom derivatizations are involved in about 80% of all heteroatom alkylation and arylation reactions in the synthesis of drug candidates.¹⁵ Thus, the development of sustainable amide-coupling techniques along with the direct nucleophilic substitution of alcohols (e.g., for preparation of amines) have been listed among the top green chemistry research priorities by the American Chemical Society Green Chemistry Pharmaceutical Roundtable (ACS GCIPR).¹⁶ Advances in employing mechanochemistry for constructing C–N bonds relevant to API synthesis, including the preparation of hydantoin derivatives,¹⁷⁻²² amides,²³⁻²⁶ bioactive peptides,^{27,28} aliphatic and aromatic amines,²⁹⁻³⁴ sulfonylurea drugs,^{35,36} hydrazones,³⁷ and sydnone³⁸ have been described in the literature.

The application of chemoselective synthetic strategies, specifically protecting-group-free methods, offers substantial benefits in the development of sustainable, cost-effective, and operationally simple manufacturing processes.^{16,39,40} This aligns with one of the 12 green

chemistry principles,² which encourages the avoidance of unnecessary derivatization. The conventional protection-deprotection approach introduces additional non-constructive steps into the synthetic route, resulting in a lower overall yield, reduced atom economy (AE),⁴¹ increased waste production,⁴² and higher costs. Although numerous studies have focused on mechanochemical amide coupling,^{23,26–28,43–49} limited attention has been given to chemoselectivity in these transformations. In particular, amide bond formation in the presence of free hydroxyl groups in the starting material has not been systematically explored, and few sporadic instances of such reactions have been reported.^{24,31,50–53} Although the nucleophilicity of amines exceeds those of alcohols and results in the predominant acylation of the former, fast reaction rates under mechanochemical conditions enabled by high concentrations of reactants might potentially result in poor chemoselectivity. While carbodiimide-mediated peptide coupling of unmasked hydroxyamino acids was shown to occur in solution,^{54,55} the reported mechanochemical examples relied on the use of hydroxyl-protecting groups in serine and tyrosine.^{27,28} In our recent works^{31,43} on mechanochemical C–N bond assembly assisted by chloro- and fluoro-*N,N,N',N'*-tetramethylformamidium hexafluorophosphates (TCFH and TFFH, Scheme 1), we noticed that TCFH selectively activates the carboxyl group in 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (**1**) to enable its amide coupling while leaving the alcoholic group intact. On the other hand, TFFH activates the alcoholic function through the generation of highly reactive isouronium intermediates that undergo facile nucleophilic substitution with amines,³¹ a transformation in which TCFH was inefficient. This observation indicates that the protecting-group-free amide coupling of hydroxycarboxylic acids can be achieved under mechanochemical conditions, with chemoselectivity governed by the selection of a C–N coupling reagent. Based on this knowledge, we aimed to undertake a screening of the previously reported

mechanochemical amide coupling protocols^{23,26,43,45} to identify the amidation approach with the highest tolerance to unmasked hydroxyl functionalities and outline the limits of such tolerance.

Here, we demonstrate that the protecting-group-free mechanochemical amide coupling of hydroxycarboxylic acids can be achieved with 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) as an optimal coupling reagent.⁴⁵ The synthetic value of the chemoselective amide-coupling methodology is illustrated by the two-step mechanochemical synthesis of imatinib (**2**), also known as Gleevec[®] (Scheme 1), an anti-cancer drug included in the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines.⁵⁶ The newly developed route to this API from 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (**1**) exhibits an enhanced safety and sustainability profile in comparison with the previously reported^{57–62} solution-based methodologies.

(a) *Previous work:*

(b) *This work:*

■ Protecting-group-free amide coupling of hydroxycarboxylic acids

■ Mechanosynthesis of Imatinib

Scheme 1. Previously reported example of a chemoselective mechanochemical amide coupling reaction³¹ and outline of this work.

Results and Discussion

At the onset, a model amide coupling reaction of **1** and 4-bromo-3-methylaniline (**8**) (Table 1) was investigated. The aromatic amine **8** was selected as a model compound because of its reduced nucleophilic properties⁶³ compared to the *N*-Boc piperazine that we used in a previous study (Scheme 1).³¹ Several known mechanochemical amidation protocols were screened to identify the conditions that enable a high-yielding preparation of amide **9**.

Table 1. Screening experiments for amide coupling of 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (**1**).^a

Entry	Coupling reagent/base	LAG additive, η ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$)	Yield of 9 , % ^b
1	TCFH/ K_2HPO_4	EtOAc (0.19)	26 ^c
2	COMU/ K_2HPO_4	EtOAc (0.19)	83 ^{d,e}
3	TCFH/NMI	Without	74 ^c
4	CDI	Without	10 ^e
5	<i>t</i> -BuOK	Without	0 ^{f,g}
6	EDC·HCl/DMAP	CH_3NO_2 (0.25)	0 ^g
7	EDC·HCl	CH_3NO_2 (0.25)	88
8	EDC·HCl	Sulfolane (0.25)	92
9	EDC·HCl	EtOAc (0.25)	90 ^h

^a General conditions: acid **1** (0.66 mmol, 100 mg), amine **8** (0.9–1 equiv.), coupling reagent (1–1.1 equiv.), base (0.85–3 equiv.), LAG additive ($\eta = 0.19$ – $0.25 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$), ball milling at 30 Hz for 60 min. See ESI for the details. ^b Yields are determined by ¹H NMR with an internal standard (1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene). ^c The guanidinium derivative **8a** was formed by the reaction of TCFH with **8**. ^d Guanidinium derivative **8b** was formed as a by-product. ^e Ester by-products that resulted from the self-condensation of **1** were observed. ^f The reaction was performed with the ethyl ester of **1**. ^g Almost no reaction: starting materials with traces of unidentified by-products. ^h Anhydride **1a** was formed in a reaction without amine **8**.

Structures of the reagents and identified by-products:

NMI = 1-methylimidazole, CDI = carbonyldiimidazole.

The test reactions were performed in a Form-Tech Scientific FTS1000 shaker mill at a 30 Hz milling frequency on a 100 mg scale in 14 mL zirconia-coated milling jars with a single 10 mm ZrO₂ (weight ca. 3 g) milling ball (see Electronic Supporting Information (ESI) for experimental details). We expected that the free hydroxyl of **1** could act as a competitive nucleophile^{64–68} that might result in a lower yield of amide **9** because of the generation of ester by-products. However, we observed various side processes, the prevalence of which was influenced by the specific coupling conditions employed. In the first experiment (Table 1, Entry 1), a combination of the TCFH reagent and K₂HPO₄ as a base in the presence of ethyl acetate as a LAG additive ($\eta = 0.19 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$) was tested. In contrast to the high-yielding coupling of **1** with *N*-Boc piperazine (Scheme 1),³¹ amide **9** was obtained with a yield of only 26%. The low yield was a consequence of the competitive reaction of TCFH with amine **8**, which resulted in guanidinium derivative **8a** (ca. 75% yield) rather than the esterification of the hydroxyl group of **1**. Switching to the (1-cyano-2-ethoxy-2-oxoethylideneaminoxy)-dimethylaminomorpholinocarbenium hexafluorophosphate (COMU) reagent (Entry 2) or replacing K₂HPO₄ with *N*-methylimidazole (Entry 3), which produces a highly reactive *N*-acyl imidazolium intermediate,⁶⁹ resulted in the formation of **9** with yields of 83% and 74%, respectively. Besides guanidinium derivative **8b** (ca. 12%), the experiment with the COMU reagent also produced oligomeric ester-type by-products that resulted from the self-condensation of **1** (characteristic ¹H NMR signals of benzylic CH₂ at δ 5.5–5.3 ppm). These by-products impeded the separation of pure amide **9** during a conventional work-up procedure that involved a simple washing of the solid reaction mixture with water and filtration. 1,1'-Carbonyldiimidazole (CDI, Entry 4)²³ resulted in a low yield of 10% of amide **9**, and the process was also accompanied by the self-condensation of **1**. Neither the amide synthesis from the ethyl ester derivative of **1** (Entry 5),²⁶ nor the combination of EDC

with 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP, Entry 6),⁴⁵ resulted in the formation of any product, leaving mostly unreacted starting materials or their mixture with some unidentified by-products, respectively. Nonetheless, the highest yield of amide **9** (88–92% by ¹H NMR) was attained with the EDC reagent⁴⁵ (Entries 7–9). Nearly complete conversion of the starting materials and absence of by-products allowed the isolation of essentially pure amide **9** with 87–89% yields by following a simple work-up protocol, which involved washing with water, filtration, and drying. By focusing on a green chemistry-inspired amendment of the method, the hazardous LAG solvent nitromethane from the original protocol⁴⁵ was replaced with the safer ethyl acetate.⁷⁰ Notably, milling of **1** with EDC, without amine **8**, resulted in the almost exclusive formation of the respective anhydride **1a**. This result indicates that EDC-activated **1** is not inclined to rapid reaction with alcohols, in contrast to activation with CDI and COMU.

Table 2. Esterification of **9** with 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (**1**).^a

Entry	Coupling reagent/base	LAG additive, η ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$)	Yield of 9a , % ^b
1	COMU/ K_2HPO_4	EtOAc (0.19)	31
2	TCFH/NMI	Without	40
3	TCFH/ K_2HPO_4	EtOAc (0.19)	5 ^c
4	EDC·HCl	EtOAc (0.25)	<1 ^d

^a General conditions: amide **9** (0.19 mmol, 60 mg), acid **1** (1 equiv.), coupling reagent (1–1.1 equiv.), base (3 equiv.), LAG additive ($\eta = 0.19\text{--}0.25 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$), ball milling at 30 Hz for 60 min. ^b Yields are determined by ¹H NMR. ^c Anhydride **1a** was formed with a 70% yield. ^d Starting materials remained and anhydride **1a** was formed with a 30% yield.

The results demonstrate that amide coupling is generally more favored with many of the tested reagent systems compared to the ester capping of the hydroxyl group. To clarify the respective chemoselectivity concerns, certain amide coupling conditions were tested

for producing ester **9a** through the reaction of **9** with **1** (see Table 2). Both the COMU/K₂HPO₄ and TCFH/NMI systems yielded **9a** at moderate yields of 31% and 40%, respectively (Table 2, Entries 1 and 2). These reagents have recently been shown to be effective for ester synthesis in solution⁷¹ and under mechanochemical conditions.⁷² However, using TCFH/K₂HPO₄ or EDC·HCl (Entries 3 and 4) resulted in only trace amounts of **9a**, with the predominant process being the generation of anhydride **1a**. In summary, the data presented in Tables 1 and 2 suggest that the COMU/K₂HPO₄ and TCFH/NMI systems are equally apt for the synthesis of both esters and amides. Therefore, when using these conditions, it is recommended to incorporate protecting groups in the starting materials to achieve optimal yields. By contrast, EDC·HCl can be reliably used for amide synthesis in the presence of unprotected hydroxyls.

We hypothesized that the nucleophilicity of the amine partner could affect yields in the amide coupling of **1** (i.e., less nucleophilic amines could deliver the respective amide products in lower yields than more nucleophilic ones). Therefore, the EDC-mediated reaction of **1** with more nucleophilic *N*-Boc piperazine and weakly nucleophilic ethyl 4-aminobenzoate was performed to verify this hypothesis (Scheme 2, a). *N*-Boc piperazine smoothly delivered amide **11** with a high yield (91%), whereas the least nucleophilic ethyl 4-aminobenzoate formed a mixture of amide **10** (76% yield) and anhydride **1a**, thus confirming that poor nucleophilic amines are less reactive, but still amenable substrates for the coupling.

Scheme 2. Scope of EDC-mediated mechanochemical amide coupling: (a) influence of amine's nucleophilicity; (b) amide coupling of aminoalcohol; (c) synthesis of amides and dipeptides from natural hydroxy (amino)acids. ^a Yield of the isolated product after washing with water, filtration, and drying in air. ^b Yield determined by ¹H NMR with an internal standard. ^c Yield of isolated product after extraction work-up. ^d Product isolated by silica gel column chromatography.

Tolerance of a free hydroxyl group in the amine partner was tested by reacting benzoic acid and (4-(aminomethyl)phenyl)methanol (Scheme 2, b). Selective acylation of the amino group was achieved affording amide **12** with a yield of 85%, but no ester isomer of **12** was formed. This outcome agrees with the analogous reactions in solution^{73,74} and those by mechanochemistry.^{24,50,51} Next, we explored the use of hydroxyl group-containing amino acids, namely *N*-Boc-*L*-serine and *N*-Boc-*L*-tyrosine, in the reaction with aniline (**8**) and *L*-phenylalanine methyl ester (Scheme 2, c). Aromatic amides **13** and **15** were prepared with high yields (82% and 90% yields, respectively) in the reactions with **8**. However, column chromatography purification was needed in these cases to

separate unreacted **8**. Dipeptides **14** and **16** were obtained with 84% and 83% yields, respectively, after washing of the reaction mixture with water and filtering (for **16**) or extraction work-up (for **14**). Dipeptide **16** was obtained as a single diastereomer (>99% *dr*), indicating that no epimerization occurred during the reaction. The synthesis of peptides **14** and **16** was previously performed in dichloromethane or dimethylformamide solutions, using carbodiimides (EDC or DCC) as coupling reagents and 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBt) as an additive.^{75,76} The reaction was much slower (over 16 h) in comparison with the essentially solvent-free and rapid (1 h) mechanochemical protocol. Lithocholic acid was chosen as an example of a steroidal hydroxy-containing natural product to highlight the scope of the reaction. The coupling of this acid with **8** produced amide **17** with a high yield (93%) after washing of the reaction mixture with water and drying in air.

The established amide-coupling conditions were applied in the synthesis of imatinib (**2**) (commercialized under the trade name of Gleevec[®]), the first rationally designed selective tyrosine kinase inhibitor launched by Novartis and approved for the treatment of chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 2001. Gleevec[®] quickly gained fame as Novartis's best-selling drug, reaching a peak of US \$4.75 billion in net sales in 2014,⁷⁷ and to this day, it remains among the top 20 best-selling products of the company's innovative medicine division⁷⁸ and is also included in the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines.⁵⁶ The first synthetic route of imatinib was patented in 1993 by Zimmermann,⁷⁹ followed by several improved protocols,^{57–62,80–85} including flow-based approaches^{86–89} and microwave-assisted solid-phase synthesis.⁹⁰ However, mechanochemical preparations have not been reported yet.

Scheme 3. The developed mechanochemical route (a) and previously reported mainstream solution-based (b) approach for the synthesis of imatinib (2).

Notably, the mainstream synthetic strategy relies on the derivatization of **1** via conversion into the corresponding chloride **3** as an additional non-constructive step that results in intermediate **5** with genotoxic properties (Scheme 3).^{58–62,81,85–88,90} The content of **5** as a trace impurity is strictly regulated in the final API (10 ppm limit).⁸² By direct derivatization of hydroxycarboxylic acid **1**, our planned route relied on the same retrosynthetic disconnection but avoided the generation of the genotoxic intermediate **5**.

Table 3. Optimization studies for the synthesis of amide **6**.^a

Entry	Coupling reagent/base	LAG additive, η ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$)	Yield of 6 , % ^b	HPLC purity of 6 , % ^c
1	EDC·HCl	EtOAc (0.25)	94	98
2	COMU/K ₂ HPO ₄	EtOAc (0.19)	81	94

^a General conditions: acid **1** (0.36 mmol, 55 mg), amine **4** (1 equiv.), coupling reagent (1–1.1 equiv.), base (3 equiv.), LAG additive ($\eta = 0.19$ – $0.25 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$), ball milling at 30 Hz for 90 min. ^b Yield of amide **6** after washing of the reaction mixture with water, filtration, and drying in air. ^c The main impurity is diacylated product **18**.

Similar to the model amide coupling of **1** with **8**, EDC performed as the best amide coupler in combination with ethyl acetate as a LAG additive ($\eta = 0.25 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$) to enable the amide coupling reaction of **1** and **4**.^{*} The corresponding amide **6** was obtained with a high yield of 94% and 98% HPLC purity after washing of the reaction mixture with water, filtration, and drying (Table 3, Entry 1). The main impurities were unreacted amine **4** (0.9%) and ester by-product **18** (1.1%). The coupling efficiency of the COMU/K₂HPO₄ system was also tested and afforded **6** with a lower yield (81%) and purity because of the greater formation of **18** (Table 3, Entry 2; see Tables S3 and S4 in the ESI for additional data). Crystals of **6** suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis were obtained by

^{*} Amine **4** is commercially available from BLDpharm, 65 €/mol.

crystallization from a methanol solution and revealed a solid-state structure, in the form of its methanol solvate.

Figure 1. Crystal structure of amide **6** (CCDC 2287665).

Nucleophilic substitution of the hydroxyl group in amide **6** with 1-methylpiperazine (**7**) was undertaken to synthesize the target API (Table 4). Amide **6** was utilized as obtained in the amide coupling reaction, without additional purification other than washing with water. Following the previously established protocol,³¹ the reaction involved the generation of a highly reactive isouronium intermediate (**6a**) and its subsequent reaction with amine **7** added to the same milling jar. The optimal reaction conditions affording the highest yield of **2** were established after performing several test runs and screening LAG additives (Table 4, see Table S5 in the ESI for additional data). Activation of the hydroxyl group in **6** was performed with TFFH (2 equiv.), using K_2HPO_4 (2.5 equiv.) and in the presence of green and biobased dimethyl isosorbide (DMI, $\eta = 0.65 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$) as the most effective LAG solvent. After 2 h of ball milling, an excess of 1-methylpiperazine (**7**) (10 equiv.) was added and the milling was continued for an additional hour. The excess of amine **7** was crucial to suppress the formation of quaternary ammonium salt by-product **19**.

Table 4. Optimization studies for the preparation of imatinib (**2**) from intermediate **6**.^a

Entry	Base	LAG additive, η ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$)	7 (equiv.)	Yield of 2 (%), ^{a,b}
1	K ₂ HPO ₄ (2 equiv.)	EtOAc (0.19)	1.5	66 ^c
2	K ₂ HPO ₄ (2.5 equiv.)	EtOAc (0.50)	5	89
3	K ₂ HPO ₄ (2.5 equiv.)	DMI (0.65)	5	93
4	K ₂ HPO ₄ (2.5 equiv.)	DMI (0.65)	10	96

^a General conditions: **6** (0.24 mmol, 100 mg), TFFH (2 equiv.), base (2–2.5 equiv.), LAG additive ($\eta = 0.19$ – $0.65 \mu\text{L mg}^{-1}$), ball milling at 30 Hz for 120 min, then, addition of 1-methylpiperazine (**7**) (1.5–10 equiv.), followed by ball milling at 30 Hz for 60 min. ^b Yield determined by HPLC analysis after washing of the reaction mixture with water and drying in air. Plausible structures of the main impurities **19** and **20** are shown below. ^c TFFH (1.5 equiv.).

By following the established optimal procedure, imatinib (**2**) was prepared from amide **6** with a high yield of 96% and 95% HPLC purity after washing of the reaction mixture with water, filtration, and drying. The same yield was achieved after scaling up the reaction threefold, from 100 mg to 300 mg loading of **6**, while still using the same 14 mL milling jar and two 10 mm milling balls. HPLC-MS analysis of the crude product revealed that the primary impurities were unreacted **6** (1.3%), quaternary salt **19** (2%), and **20** (1.4%). Further purification of the crude product (**2**) was achieved through recrystallization from a methanol-ethyl acetate mixture (1:1 ratio), yielding the target API with an HPLC purity of 99%. The main contaminants were **20** (0.1%) and the starting amide **6** (0.7%).

To reveal the advantages and drawbacks of the developed mechanochemical synthesis, the first-pass green chemistry metrics were assessed using the CHEM21 toolkit (Table 5).⁴¹ To perform a reliable comparison with the solution-based approaches, we selected the known synthetic routes that rely on the same retrosynthetic disconnection and start from the same building blocks **1**, **4**, and **7** (Scheme 3). Among them,^{57–62} the shortest route for which the complete data were available for the calculations⁹¹ was an early-stage development described by Liu et al.⁵⁹ and an example of kilo-scale preparation patented by Natco Pharma Ltd.⁶⁰ Activation of hydroxy acid **1** by its conversion to the corresponding chloride via reaction with SOCl₂ was used in both approaches as an additional non-constructive step.

Table 5. Comparison of green metrics for mechanochemical and similar solution-based approaches for the synthesis of imatinib (**2**).^a

	Liu et al. ⁵⁹	Natco Pharma Ltd. ⁶⁰	This work
<i>Number of constructive/total steps</i>	2/3	2/3	2/2
<i>Mass of the product</i>	0.450 g	9.8 kg	0.66 g
<i>Total yield</i>	85	43	86 ^b
<i>AE</i>	50.9	50.9	39.1
<i>RME</i>	3.8	13.2	17.0
<i>Total PMI</i>	563.5	192.2	221.0
<i>PMI reaction</i>	43.5	46.6	8.9
<i>PMI reaction solvents</i>	17	39.0	3.0
<i>PMI work-up solvents</i>	520	144.6	212.1
<i>Solvents</i>	CH ₂ Cl ₂ , THF, H ₂ O	DMF, CHCl ₃ , Toluene, EtOAc, H ₂ O	EtOAc, DMI, H ₂ O
<i>Isolation procedure</i>	Water treatment, filtration	Extraction	Water treatment, filtration
<i>Hazards:</i>			
<i>Thermal</i>	140 °C	60 °C	r.t.
<i>Reagent/solvent</i>	-	DMF (H360), CHCl ₃ (H372)	EDC (H410)
<i>Products</i>	SO ₂ , HCl	SO ₂ , HCl	TMU ^c (H360)
<i>Genotoxic intermediates</i>	5 4	5 4	- 4

^a Extended data and calculations for similar routes, for which full experimental details are unavailable are also shown in the ESI (Table S8). ^b The yield is adjusted considering the HPLC purity (95%) of the obtained product. ^c TMU = tetramethyl urea.

The mass-based metrics were calculated considering all steps of the respective preparation route (see ESI for the details). In terms of total yield (86%), the mechanochemical approach delivered comparable or superior results as the benchmark solution-state approaches. Atom economy (AE), which reflects the theoretical efficiency of reactant utilization, is lower in the mechanochemical route (AE = 39.1) because of the higher molecular weight of the reagents involved. However, reaction mass efficiency (RME), which represents the actual maximum efficiency of reactant utilization,⁴¹ is noticeably higher (RME = 17.0) than those of the solution-based protocols, in which a greater excess of chemicals was used. Finally, total process mass intensity (total PMI), which reflects the amount of waste generated per unit of product, is approximately 2.5 times lower than in a similar early-stage development solution route (PMI = 563.5 vs. 221.0) and is comparable with the PMI of a kilo-scale preparation (PMI = 192.2). It is important to note that the main contributor to PMI in the case of mechanochemical synthesis is the work-up solvent (water, PMI = 212.1) rather than chemicals (PMI = 8.9) and reaction solvents (PMI = 3.0). In terms of the former two, the mechanochemical route greatly surpasses the benchmarking solution approaches, in which excess reactants and the use of bulk solvents substantially increase the PMI. Furthermore, the mechanochemical protocol relies on the use of eco-friendly solvents for work-up (water) and as LAG additives (ethyl acetate and dimethyl isosorbide). This contrasts with the larger portfolio of solvents involved in the solution-based preparations as that includes several toxic compounds (DMF, CH₂Cl₂, and chloroform). It is also worth noting that the room temperature operation is an additional benefit of mechanochemistry, in contrast to the solution methods, which rely on thermal activation and involve heating up to 140 °C. The streamlined isolation protocol of **6** and **2** by filtration and washing with water has an additional advantage. Although the solvent-related and thermal hazards have been greatly

attenuated in our approach, it still relies on the use of stoichiometric amide-coupling reagents (EDC and TFFH), which themselves or their reaction products (e.g., tetramethyl urea, TMU), could pose environmental or health hazards,⁹² thus representing a disadvantage. On the other hand, TFFH is an air-stable and non-hygroscopic solid that offers a better safety profile^{92,93} than other amide couplers.

To present the green chemistry-related innovations of the developed method even more clearly, we applied the “innovation Green Aspiration Level” (iGAL) methodology⁹⁴ using the respective scorecard web calculator.⁹⁵ The mechanochemical method demonstrated an excellent relative process greenness (RPG) of 77%, which is much higher than that of the RPG (30%) of the solution-based method by Liu et al., which was used as a benchmark early-stage development process (Figure 2). Moreover, the mechanochemical approach exhibits a waste output 2.22 times lower than that of the average value at the early development stage.

Exclusion of the genotoxic intermediate **5** is another crucial advantage, which is especially relevant to pharma synthesis. Because intermediate **6** with unknown properties was involved instead, an additional *in silico* assessment was performed for the designed route to evaluate the safety profile of all known chemical entities involved. Knowledge-based and statistical systems were used to predict potential mutagenicity following the recommendations of the ICH M7 (R1) (2018) guideline. Derek Nexus (a knowledge-based system) and Sarah Nexus (a statistical system) were used to predict mutagenicity. Derek Nexus (Lhasa Ltd., Leeds, UK), is a rule-based expert system, which has been designed on the basis of open, accessible, and proprietary data. Derek Nexus generates predictions based on the knowledge about the relationship between substructures and biological activity in a given molecule. In Sarah Nexus (Lhasa Ltd., Leeds, UK), structures submitted for processing are fragmented and these fragments are reviewed for

activity vs. inactivity. The model then arranges those “interesting” fragments into a network of hypotheses (or nodes) and relevant hypotheses are used to inform an overall prediction of toxicity. Sarah Nexus predicts activity or inactivity in the Ames test and provides information on the coverage of a query compound. As a result, intermediate **6** displayed no structural concern for mutagenicity. However, genotoxic amine **4** was still involved as a starting material, which represents a disadvantage. The European Pharmacopoeia guidelines⁹⁶ were followed (see ESI) to determine the content of **4** in the product, and revealed the presence of **4** at a concentration of ca. 560 ppm. However, further optimization of downstream processing protocols (see ESI, Section 6) allowed for the reduction of its content to ca. 90 ppm. Although this value still exceeds the established 20 ppm threshold, it is similar to the content in the crude imatinib obtained by other methods⁹⁷ and could be minimized during downstream processing.⁹⁷

Figure 2. Graphical illustration of green chemistry innovation by the iGAL scorecard.

Conclusions

Here, we demonstrated that mechanochemical amide coupling can be performed with unprotected hydroxycarboxylic acids, using EDC as the most chemoselective coupling reagent in combination with ethyl acetate as a green LAG additive. High amide yields (76–94%) can be achieved, and the use of poor nucleophilic amines results in reduced coupling efficacy. The presence of an unmasked hydroxyl group in the obtained amide products allows their straightforward functionalization in a step-economical manner such as the nucleophilic substitution of the hydroxyl group. This procedure is illustrated by the first mechanochemical synthesis of imatinib, an anticancer drug included in the World Health Organization’s List of Essential Medicines. The target API was prepared with an 86% total yield and HPLC purity of 99% through a two-fold C–N bond construction sequence, which involved EDC-mediated amide coupling of 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (**1**) with aromatic amine **4**, followed by nucleophilic substitution of the isouronium-activated hydroxyl group in the amide intermediate **6** with 1-methylpiperazine (**7**). Green chemistry benefits and hot spots of the developed route were revealed through the analysis of relevant metrics, conducted using CHEM21 and iGAL tools. The analysis demonstrated that the proposed mechanochemical method is a safer and more sustainable alternative for the synthesis of imatinib, in contrast to the mainstream solution-based methods. We believe that the proposed methodology could be expanded onto the preparation of similar pharmaceuticals,^{98–101} thus improving the green chemistry performance of the existing synthetic methods.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Estonian Research Council grant PRG399 and COST Action CA18112 “Mechanochemistry for Sustainable Industry.” This project received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2021–2027 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101057286 (IMPACTIVE). Danylo Merzhyievskiy is grateful to the Education and Youth Board of Estonia for the financial support of his research stay at Tallinn University of Technology.

References

- 1 S. Kar, H. Sanderson, K. Roy, E. Benfenati and J. Leszczynski, *Chem. Rev.*, 2022, **122**, 3637–3710.
- 2 P. T. Anastas and J. C. Warner, *Green Chemistry: Theory and Practice*, Oxford University Press: New York, 1998.
- 3 S. L. James, C. J. Adams, C. Bolm, D. Braga, P. Collier, T. Friščić, F. Grepioni, K. D. M. Harris, G. Hyett, W. Jones, A. Krebs, J. Mack, L. Maini, A. G. Orpen, I. P. Parkin, W. C. Shearouse, J. W. Steed and D. C. Waddell, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 413–447.
- 4 J. L. Howard, Q. Cao and D. L. Browne, *Chem. Sci.*, 2018, **9**, 3080–3094.
- 5 T. Friščić, C. Mottillo and H. M. Titi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2020, **59**, 1018–1029.
- 6 E. Colacino, F. Delogu and T. Hanusa, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2021, **9**, 10662–10663.
- 7 D. Tan, L. Loots and T. Friščić, *Chem. Commun.*, 2016, **52**, 7760–7781.
- 8 P. Ying, J. Yu and W. Su, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2021, **363**, 1246–1271.
- 9 O. Bento, F. Luttringer, T. Mohy El Dine, N. Pétry, X. Bantreil and F. Lamaty, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2022, e202101516.
- 10 X. Yang, C. Wu, W. Su and J. Yu, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2022, e202101440.
- 11 M. Pérez-Venegas and E. Juaristi, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2020, **8**, 8881–8893.
- 12 O. Galant, G. Cerfeda, A. S. McCalmont, S. L. James, A. Porcheddu, F. Delogu, D. E. Crawford, E. Colacino and S. Spatari, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2022, **10**, 1430–1439.
- 13 D. J. C. Constable, C. Jimenez-Gonzalez and R. K. Henderson, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2007, **11**, 133–137.
- 14 P. Ertl, E. Altmann and J. M. McKenna, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2020, **63**, 8408–8418.
- 15 S. D. Roughley and A. M. Jordan, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **54**, 3451–3479.
- 16 M. C. Bryan, P. J. Dunn, D. Entwistle, F. Gallou, S. G. Koenig, J. D. Hayler, M. R. Hickey, S. Hughes, M. E. Kopach, G. Moine, P. Richardson, F. Roschangar, A. Steven and F. J. Weiberth, *Green Chem.*, 2018, **20**, 5082–5103.
- 17 E. Colacino, A. Porcheddu, C. Charnay and F. Delogu, *React. Chem. Eng.*, 2019, **4**, 1179–1188.
- 18 L. Konnert, B. Reneaud, R. M. de Figueiredo, J.-M. Campagne, F. Lamaty, J. Martinez and E. Colacino, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2014, **79**, 10132–10142.
- 19 L. Konnert, M. Dimassi, L. Gonnet, F. Lamaty, J. Martinez and E. Colacino, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 36978–36986.
- 20 A. Mascitti, M. Lupacchini, R. Guerra, I. Taydakov, L. Tonucci, N. d’Alessandro, F. Lamaty, J. Martinez and E. Colacino, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.*, 2017, **13**, 19–25.
- 21 E. Colacino, A. Porcheddu, I. Halasz, C. Charnay, F. Delogu, R. Guerra and J. Fullenwarth, *Green Chem.*, 2018, **20**, 2973–2977.
- 22 D. E. Crawford, A. Porcheddu, A. S. McCalmont, F. Delogu, S. L. James and E. Colacino, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2020, **8**, 12230–12238.
- 23 T.-X. Métro, J. Bonnamour, T. Reidon, J. Sarpoulet, J. Martinez and F. Lamaty, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 11781–11783.
- 24 T. Portada, D. Margetić and V. Štrukil, *Molecules*, 2018, **23**, 3163.
- 25 M. Lavayssiere and F. Lamaty, *Chem. Commun.*, 2023, **59**, 3439–3442.
- 26 W. I. Nicholson, F. Barreteau, J. A. Leitch, R. Payne, I. Priestley, E. Godineau, C. Battilocchio and D. L. Browne, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2021, **60**, 21868–21874.
- 27 L. Gonnet, T. Tintillier, N. Venturini, L. Konnert, J.-F. Hernandez, F. Lamaty, G. Laconde, J. Martinez and E. Colacino, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2017, **5**, 2936–2941.
- 28 J. Bonnamour, T.-X. Métro, J. Martinez and F. Lamaty, *Green Chem.*, 2013, **15**, 1116–1120.

- 29 M. Pérez-Venegas and E. Juaristi, *Tetrahedron*, 2018, **74**, 6453–6458.
- 30 V. Canale, W. Trybała, S. Chaumont-Dubel, P. Koczurkiewicz-Adamczyk, G. Satała, O. Bento, K. Blicharz-Futera, X. Bantreil, E. Pękala, A. J. Bojarski, F. Lamaty, P. Marin and P. Zajdel, *Biomolecules*, 2023, **13**, 12.
- 31 T. Dalidovich, J. V. Nallaparaju, T. Shalima, R. Aav and D. G. Kananovich, *ChemSusChem*, 2022, **15**, e202102286.
- 32 Q.-L. Shao, Z.-J. Jiang and W.-K. Su, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2018, **59**, 2277–2280.
- 33 Q. Cao, W. I. Nicholson, A. C. Jones and D. L. Browne, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2019, **17**, 1722–1726.
- 34 K. Kubota, T. Seo, K. Koide, Y. Hasegawa and H. Ito, *Nat. Commun.*, 2019, **10**, 111.
- 35 D. Tan, V. Štrukil, C. Mottillo and T. Friščić, *Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **50**, 5248–5250.
- 36 E. Colacino, G. Dayaker, A. Morère and T. Friščić, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 2019, **96**, 766–771.
- 37 P. F. M. Oliveira, M. Baron, A. Chamayou, C. André-Barrès, B. Guidetti and M. Baltas, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 56736–56742.
- 38 N. Pétry, F. Luttringer, X. Bantreil and F. Lamaty, *Faraday Discuss.*, 2023, **241**, 114–127.
- 39 D. J. C. Constable, P. J. Dunn, J. D. Hayler, G. R. Humphrey, Jr. Leazer Johnnie L., R. J. Linderman, K. Lorenz, J. Manley, B. A. Pearlman, A. Wells, A. Zaks and T. Y. Zhang, *Green Chem.*, 2007, **9**, 411–420.
- 40 R. Ramesh, S. Sonawane, D. S. Reddy and R. Bandichhor, in *Protecting-Group-Free Organic Synthesis*, ed. R. A. Fernandes, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, 2018, 6, pp. 155–181.
- 41 C. R. McElroy, A. Constantinou, L. C. Jones, L. Summerton and J. H. Clark, *Green Chem.*, 2015, **17**, 3111–3121.
- 42 R. A. Sheldon, *Green Chem.*, 2007, **9**, 1273–1283.
- 43 T. Dalidovich, K. A. Mishra, T. Shalima, M. Kudrjašova, D. G. Kananovich and R. Aav, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2020, **8**, 15703–15715.
- 44 C. Bolm and J. G. Hernández, *ChemSusChem*, 2018, **11**, 1410–1420.
- 45 V. Štrukil, B. Bartolec, T. Portada, I. Đilović, I. Halasz and D. Margetić, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 12100–12102.
- 46 V. Porte, M. Thioly, T. Pigoux, T.-X. Métro, J. Martinez and F. Lamaty, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2016, 3505–3508.
- 47 C. Duangkamol, S. Jaita, S. Wangngae, W. Phakhodee and M. Pattarawarapan, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 52624–52628.
- 48 T. Lainer, F. Czerny and M. Haas, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2022, **20**, 3717–3720.
- 49 J. G. Hernández, K. J. Ardila-Fierro, D. Crawford, S. L. James and C. Bolm, *Green Chem.*, 2017, **19**, 2620–2625.
- 50 Q. Cao, D. E. Crawford, C. Shi and S. L. James, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2020, **59**, 4478–4483.
- 51 F. Ravalico, S. L. James and J. S. Vyle, *Green Chem.*, 2011, **13**, 1778–1783.
- 52 M. Anselmi, P. Stavole, E. Boanini, A. Bigi, E. Juaristi and L. Gentilucci, *Future Med. Chem.*, 2020, **12**, 479–491.
- 53 F. Santino, R. Petruzzelli, J. Zhao, E. Boanini and L. Gentilucci, *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.*, 2021, **24**, 100540.
- 54 Y. Zhang, J. Feng, C. Liu, H. Fang and W. Xu, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **19**, 4437–4444.
- 55 A. K. Bose, M. S. Manhas, D. P. Sahu and V. R. Hegde, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1984, **62**, 2498–2505.
- 56 WHO Model List of Essential Medicines, 22nd List; World Health Organization, 2021.

- 57 M. D. Khunt, N. S. Patil, H. S. Pagire and N. S. Pradhan, *World Pat.*, 2011095835A1, 2011.
- 58 Y. Heo, D. Hyun, M. R. Kumar, H. M. Jung and S. Lee, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2012, **53**, 6657–6661.
- 59 Y.-F. Liu, C.-L. Wang, Y.-J. Bai, N. Han, J.-P. Jiao and X.-L. Qi, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2008, **12**, 490–495.
- 60 A. Kompella, A. K. S. Bhujanga Rao, N. Venkaiah Chowdary and R. Srinivas, *World Pat.*, 2004108699A1, 2004.
- 61 Z. Szakács, S. Béni, Z. Varga, L. Örfi, G. Kéri and B. Noszál, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **48**, 249–255.
- 62 W. Szczepiek, W. Luniewski, L. Kaczmarek, B. Zagrodzki, D. Samson-Lazinska, W. Szelejewski and M. Skarzynski, *World Pat.*, 2006071130A2, 2006.
- 63 T. Kanzian, T. A. Nigst, A. Maier, S. Pichl and H. Mayr, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, 6379–6385.
- 64 M. Tsakos, E. S. Schaffert, L. L. Clement, N. L. Villadsen and T. B. Poulsen, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 2015, **32**, 605–632.
- 65 B. Neises and W. Steglich, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1978, **17**, 522–524.
- 66 A. Chighine, S. Crosignani, M.-C. Arnal, M. Bradley and B. Linclau, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 4753–4762.
- 67 J. K. Twibanire and T. B. Grindley, *Org. Lett.*, 2011, **13**, 2988–2991.
- 68 M. K. Pittelkow Fadhil S; Boas, Ulrik; Pedersen, Brian; Christensen, Jørn B., *Synthesis*, 2004, 2485–2492.
- 69 G. L. Beutner, I. S. Young, M. L. Davies, M. R. Hickey, H. Park, J. M. Stevens and Q. Ye, *Org. Lett.*, 2018, **20**, 4218–4222.
- 70 D. Prat, A. Wells, J. Hayler, H. Sneddon, C. R. McElroy, S. Abou-Shehada and P. J. Dunn, *Green Chem.*, 2016, **18**, 288–296.
- 71 N. R. Luis, K. K. Chung, M. R. Hickey, Z. Lin, G. L. Beutner and D. A. Vosburg, *Org. Lett.*, DOI:10.1021/acs.orglett.3c01611.
- 72 H. Nishikawa, M. Kuwayama, A. Nihonyanagi, B. Dhara and F. Araoka, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, DOI:10.1039/D3TC02212A.
- 73 D.-K. Kim, J. Y. Lee, J.-S. Kim, J.-H. Ryu, J.-Y. Choi, J. W. Lee, G.-J. Im, T.-K. Kim, J. W. Seo, H.-J. Park, J. Yoo, J.-H. Park, T.-Y. Kim and Y.-J. Bang, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 5745–5751.
- 74 M. Parmentier, M. K. Wagner, K. Magra and F. Gallou, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2016, **20**, 1104–1107.
- 75 I. Lazouni, J. Pérard-Viret, K. Hammad and W. Drici, *ARKIVOC*, 2022, 23–37.
- 76 S. Bera, P. Jana, S. K. Maity and D. Haldar, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2014, **14**, 1032–1038.
- 77 <https://www.novartis.com/investors/novartis-annual-reporting-suite/reporting-archive> Novartis Annual Report 2014, 2015.
- 78 <https://www.novartis.com/investors/financial-data/product-sales>, 2022.
- 79 Zimmermann, J. EP Patent, 0564409, 1993.
- 80 B. J. Deadman, M. D. Hopkin, I. R. Baxendale and S. V. Ley, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2013, **11**, 1766–1800.
- 81 X. Zhang, J. Sun, T. Chen, C. Yang, L. Yu, *Synlett*, 2016, **27**, 2233–2236.
- 82 A. Kompella, B. R. K. Adibhatla, P. R. Muddasani, S. Rachakonda, V. K. Gampa and P. K. Dubey, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2012, **16**, 1794–1804.
- 83 K. C. Nicolaou, D. Vourloumis, S. Totokotsopoulos, A. Papakyriakou, H. Karsunky, H. Fernando, J. Gavrilyuk, D. Webb and A. F. Stepan, *ChemMedChem*, 2016, **11**, 31–37.

- 84 C. Wang, X. Bai, R. Wang, X. Zheng, X. Ma, H. Chen, Y. Ai, Y. Bai and Y. Liu, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2019, **23**, 1918–1925.
- 85 O. Loiseleur, D. Kaufmann, S. Abel, H. M. Buerger, M. Meisenbach, B. Schmitz, G. N. Sedelmeier, World Pat. 2003066613, 2003.
- 86 M. D. Hopkin, I. R. Baxendale and S. V. Ley, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 2450–2452.
- 87 J. C. Yang, D. Niu, B. P. Karsten, F. Lima and S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2016, **55**, 2531–2535.
- 88 N. Collins, D. Stout, J.-P. Lim, J. P. Malerich, J. D. White, P. B. Madrid, M. Latendresse, D. Krieger, J. Szeto, V.-A. Vu, K. Rucker, M. Deleo, Y. Gorfu, M. Krummenacker, L. A. Hokama, P. Karp and S. Mallya, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2020, **24**, 2064–2077.
- 89 W. C. Fu and T. F. Jamison, *Org. Lett.*, 2019, **21**, 6112–6116.
- 90 F. Leonetti, C. Capaldi and A. Carotti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 3455–3458.
- 91 Note: The calculations for analogous routes (where full experimental details are unavailable) are additionally presented in the ESI (Table S6).
- 92 J. C. Graham, A. Trejo-Martin, M. L. Chilton, J. Kostal, J. Bercu, G. L. Beutner, U. S. Bruen, D. G. Dolan, S. Gomez, J. Hillegass, J. Nicolette and M. Schmitz, *Chem. Res. Toxicol.*, 2022, **35**, 1011–1022.
- 93 J. B. Sperry, C. J. Minter, J. Tao, R. Johnson, R. Duzguner, M. Hawksworth, S. Oke, P. F. Richardson, R. Barnhart, D. R. Bill, R. A. Giusto and J. D. I. Weaver, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2018, **22**, 1262–1275.
- 94 F. Roschangar, Y. Zhou, D. J. C. Constable, J. Colberg, D. P. Dickson, P. J. Dunn, M. D. Eastgate, F. Gallou, J. D. Hayler, S. G. Koenig, M. E. Kopach, D. K. Leahy, I. Mergelsberg, U. Scholz, A. G. Smith, M. Henry, J. Mulder, J. Brandenburg, J. R. Dehli, D. R. Fandrick, K. R. Fandrick, F. Gnad-Badouin, G. Zerban, K. Groll, P. T. Anastas, R. A. Sheldon and C. H. Senanayake, *Green Chem.*, 2018, **20**, 2206–2211.
- 95 <https://www.acs.org/green-chemistry-innovation-scorecard>, 2023.
- 96 European pharmacopoeia 9.2, 07/2017:2736, Imatinib Mesilate, 2017.
- 97 E. Grendele, A. Soldà, Eur. Pat., 2927223B1, 2015.
- 98 B. J. Druker, S. Tamura, E. Buchdunger, S. Ohno, G. M. Segal, S. Fanning, J. Zimmermann and N. B. Lydon, *Nat. Med.*, 1996, **2**, 561–566.
- 99 K. A. Hahn, G. Oglivie, T. Rusk, P. Devauchelle, A. Leblanc, A. Legendre, B. Powers, P. S. Leventhal, J.-P. Kinet, F. Palmerini, P. Dubreuil, A. Moussy and O. Hermine, *J. Vet. Intern. Med.*, 2008, **22**, 1301–1309.
- 100 T. Suzuki, T. Ando, K. Tsuchiya, N. Fukazawa, A. Saito, Y. Mariko, T. Yamashita and O. Nakanishi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1999, **42**, 3001–3003.
- 101 M. A. Letavic, L. Aluisio, R. Apodaca, M. Bajpai, A. J. Barbier, A. Bonneville, P. Bonaventure, N. I. Carruthers, C. Dugovic, I. C. Fraser, M. L. Kramer, B. Lord, T. W. Lovenberg, L. Y. Li, K. S. Ly, H. Mcallister, N. S. Mani, K. L. Morton, A. Ndifor, S. D. Nepomuceno, C. R. Pandit, S. B. Sands, C. R. Shah, J. E. Shelton, S. S. Snook, D. M. Swanson and W. Xiao, *ACS Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2015, **6**, 450–454.

Graphical abstract:

The mechanochemical protecting-group-free amidation of hydroxycarboxylic acids is presented. The transformation is applied to the synthesis of imatinib via a two-fold C–N bond construction sequence that bypasses a chlorinated genotoxic intermediate.